

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Wave 2 Questionnaire

User module “Intensive parenting”

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User Modules in the GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire

The GGS-II Wave 2 questionnaire was restructured to include new thematic sections, with space allocated for user-driven innovations. In 2023, an open call invited researchers to submit new content modules. The proposals were evaluated by a selection committee based on their scientific novelty and relevance to the GGS.

Five user modules were selected and integrated into the questionnaire, offering fresh insights into family dynamics, fertility, and related topics. This working paper series contains revised versions of the original submissions, including the finalized questions that were ultimately incorporated into the Wave 2 questionnaire.

Andersson, G., Neyer, G., Lappegård, T., & Bujard, M. (2024). *User module: "Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044105

Berrington, A., & Perelli-Harris, B. (2024). *User module: "Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044047

Billingsley, S., Mollborn, S., Olah, L., & Duvander, A.-Z. (2024). *User module: "Intensive Parenting"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14043910

Mortelmans, D., Lück, D., Claessens, E., Van Gasse, D., Bujard, M., & Frembs, L. (2024). *User module: "Singlehood"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044075

Rouvroye, L., Fischer, M., Rampazzo, F., van der Vleuten, M., Fortes De Lena, F., Pao, C., de Vries, L., & Jin, Y. (2024). *User module: "Sexual Orientation"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044062

Abstract

Norms encouraging "intensive parenting" have become pervasive in many wealthy countries and across social strata, pressuring parents to take increased personal responsibility for ensuring children's well-being and success. These norms have been argued to be motivated by concerns about protecting children's future social status. How strong and universal these norms are across diverse contexts is unknown due to a lack of comparative data. The extent to which these norms have proliferated may differ depending on state support of parenthood and childbearing and the extent of recent increases in inequality. Questions measuring multiple dimensions of intensive parenting norms and attitudes in GGS data allow exploration of their prevalence and composition across contexts and differences according to social class, gender, cohort, parenthood status, family structure, and family background. We are further able to identify family profiles mapping household division of labour onto intensive parenting attitudes. The implications of intensive parenting norms for demographic and social outcomes are also poorly understood. The structure and content of GGS facilitates assessment of how intensive parenting norms are related to: 1) multiple dimensions of adults' well-being, 2) childbearing plans, and 3) labour market engagement following childbirth.

Motivation and scientific foundation

We have long known that material resources matter for giving children the best start in life, and 20th century research also increasingly recognized the importance of interpersonal interactions between parents and children in shaping children's development and well-being. Authoritative parenting, characterized by high support and high control of children, was previously considered the preferred parenting style (Steinberg et al. 1989). By the 1990s, US norms were evolving regarding not only how to parent but also how much time and energy to spend on parenting. These norms regulating how to be a “good” parent have been labelled “intensive parenting” and involve “child-centered, expert-guided, emotionally absorbing, labour intensive, and financially expensive” parenting practices aimed to advance children’s social and cognitive development (Hays 1996, p.8). Through “concerted cultivation” (Lareau 2003), parents directly engage with children’s development through providing educational, social, and creative opportunities, in contrast to the “natural growth” approach in which parents meet basic needs and allow the child to develop naturally while deferring to the authority of professionals.

Parents spend substantially more money and time on their children than ever before (e.g., Doti Sani Giulia & Treas 2016). The amount of care both mothers and fathers give their children has increased in the US over recent decades, even as mothers have spent more time in the labour market (Bianchi 2011). While such quantitative research has tended to focus on the “how much” of intensive parenting, qualitative research has unpacked the “how,” tapping into norms and attitudes. (Norms at the group level regulate expectations for behaviour, while attitudes are held by individuals and often but not always reflect the norms held by the individual’s group (Cooper, Kelly & Weaver 2001).) US qualitative and ethnographic research such as Hays’ (1996) and Lareau’s (2003) developed our initial understanding of variation and change in parenting norms and generated a continually expanding field of intensive parenting research (e.g., Budds et al. 2017; Christopher 2012; Lee 2008). More recently, quantitative research using surveys has expanded into the “how,” documenting widespread intensive parenting norms and their correlates (Gauthier et al. 2021; Loyal et al. 2017; Mackintosh et al. 2014; Ishizuka 2019).

Although intensive parenting has been well documented in the US and is considered the hegemonic parenting paradigm (Damaske 2013), little is known about how intensive parenting has developed outside the US context. Neoliberal trends and the increasing individualization of health in the US and elsewhere (Lebesco 2011) have strengthened the notion that parents are personally responsible for ensuring their children’s well-being through their own actions. Besides supporting children in becoming good people with high-quality interpersonal relationships who contribute to society, one clear underlying motivation of intensive parenting is to protect the social status of one’s children and facilitate their social mobility (Milkie & Warner 2014; Gauthier & de Jong 2021). The latter motivation could be unique to contexts with high social inequality and restricted opportunities for upward mobility such as the US. In societies where the cost of continued education is subsidized by the state, providing greater opportunities for upward mobility, there may have been less development of parenting practices aiming

to give one's child every possible advantage. Nevertheless, diffusion or development of these norms is likely not restricted to a single context, especially in light of the globalization and digitalization of information that have ramped up the speed and spread of international research findings that inform parenting practices.

A few studies have demonstrated through surveys that intensive parenting attitudes are now present in France (Loyal et al. 2017), Estonia, Great Britain, and Slovenia (Gauthier et al. 2021). Although the instruments used in these studies are similar, directly comparable measures across a wide range of countries do not yet exist. Comparing responses to intensive parenting items across many countries documents the extent of the spread of intensive parenting norms internationally. This multinational comparison could also clarify the role of state support for parents and for gender equality in mitigating the intensification of intensive parenting norms, a research question that previous scholarship has been unable to address.

The questions that we propose are based primarily on the Intensive Parenting Attitudes Questionnaire (IPAQ-25), which was developed and validated by a team of psychologists (Liss et al. 2013). It includes 25 questions that cover five dimensions of intensive parenting and was validated in the French context as well (Loyal et al. 2017). Three of these five dimensions were new to the GGS (child-centeredness, stimulation and demanding), whereas two dimensions had been previously covered in questions that were part of the GGS core questionnaire and used to study gender roles (essentialism and fulfilment). In the Swedish GGS that was administered in 2021, the three new dimensions were represented by two distinct measures each. This data is being analysed now, and we see expected and unexpected differences in agreement with these attitudes across the Swedish sample, as well as strong links to fertility intentions.

We continue to focus on three dimensions and forego essentialism and fulfilment measures because, as argued in Gauthier et al. (2021), these three are the domains in which we would expect to see an intensification of parenting. To ensure that each of these three dimensions meets the minimum survey item construction guidelines suggested for methods such as structural equation modelling and confirmatory factor analysis (Robinson 2018), we have expanded the survey questions to have 3 items per dimension instead of 2, which may also increase the interest from other disciplines in these measures. The additional item added to each dimension also comes from the IPAQ-25. The items were selected based on more recent investigations of intensive parenting in a cross-national comparison using CRONOS data (a survey attached to the ESS and administered to a portion of the ESS samples in 2017 in Great Britain, Estonia and Slovenia) and an ongoing pilot study in Poland (under the direction of Monika Mynarska and Marta Bryzek at the Institute of Psychology, Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University), in which these questions were tested and analysed in terms of performance as a scale.

Relevance to GGS-II wave 2 and all countries

The 2nd wave proposal for GGS has very few attitudinal questions now, leaving room for new attitudinal measures such as those on intensive parenting. The subject fits very well alongside core GGS questions as it pertains to norms and attitudes that govern parenting, intergenerational relations, and family life. The core GGS questions do not include any measures that are suitable for assessing the intensity of parenting norms and attitudes.

In terms of other potential comparative surveys, implementing them in the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) would provide a wide range of reproductive questions that could be related to intensive parenting norms, but it would not provide the possibility to consider the wide range of correlates that GGS provides, including the organization of family life, working life, and general well-being and health. DHS are primarily administered to women and are concentrated in countries in which working life is not assumed to be an important focus in women's lives. Research about the prevalence and implications of intensive parenting norms need not be limited to women; the comparison with men can provide a deeper gendered understanding of how these norms are internalized. In contrast, the European Social Survey would offer a similar range of middle to high income countries as GGS, but would not provide the capacity to connect parenting norms to past, current and potentially future family life to the extent that GGS would.

The new broadened scope of GGS countries is an excellent development from the perspective of intensive parenting research. Evidence has shown that intensive parenting norms can be identified in countries as diverse as Chile (Diaz 2021), old welfare democracies (US and Great Britain), and Eastern European countries (Estonia and Slovenia) (Gauthier et al. 2021). The broadened range of countries being surveyed in the new GGS wave provides exciting opportunities to continue assessing the spread and cultural specificities of intensive parenting norms.

The survey questions are suitable for repeated cross-sectional design, but a longitudinal design provides several opportunities to explore predictors and outcomes correlated with adherence to intensive parenting norms. First, because there is no evidence supporting substantive change in attitudes between waves of panel data, the introduction of intensive parenting attitudes in wave two allows analyses of how they are related to values and attitudinal measures in wave one. Second, adding these questions in wave 2 allows us to establish a baseline measure of individuals' parenting approach to use in future waves. Questions related to the realization of fertility intentions can only be addressed with a longitudinal design, as well as how intensive parenting shapes work trajectories after entering parenthood or having a subsequent child. Third, we have the possibility with wave two questions to explore how behaviours at time one may relate to attitudes at time two. In sum, this research design makes intensive parenting questions broadly useful for current and future research as both a predictor and an outcome.

Survey questions

INTintro (*Intensive parenting Intro*) (Empty)

The next section will ask general questions about your views on parenting nowadays. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements.

b12INT01A (*Parents never get a mental break from their children*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Parents never get a mental break from their children, even when they are physically apart

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01B (*It is important for children to be involved in activities that stimulate them*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Beyond regular school classes, it is important for children to be involved in classes, lessons, and activities that engage and stimulate them

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01C (*Childrearing is a really demanding job*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Childrearing is a really demanding job

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01D (*Children should be the center of their parents' attention*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Children should be the center of their parents' attention

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01E (*Finding the best pre-school educational opportunities for children is important*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Finding the best educational opportunities for children is important even before they go to school

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01F (*Children's needs should come before their parents'*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Children's needs should come before their parents'

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01G (*Being a parent means never having time for oneself*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Being a parent means never having time for oneself

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01H (*The child's schedule should take priority*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The child's schedule should take priority over the needs of the parents

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01I (*It is important to interact regularly with children on their level*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

It is important to interact regularly with children on their level (e.g., getting down on the floor and playing with them)

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

Translation guide for Intensive parenting questions

1. Module location and introduction

The IP module is located between the PAR (parental home) and ECR (Economic activity) sections. The introduction to the module should make it clear that the subsequent questions are related to parenting attitudes / norms nowadays. The following sentence was chosen to ensure that we get at individual attitudes and not just norms.

“The next section will ask general questions about your views on parenting nowadays. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with each of statements”

2. Although the response to the following items may very much depend on age, this is an empirical question and therefore the translations should not add any age-specific terms: “Children should be the centre of their parents’ attention” and “The child’s schedule should take priority over the needs of the parents”.

3. In the question “Beyond regular school classes, it is important for children to be involved in classes, lessons, and activities that engage and stimulate them”, the question refers to activities that may take place at the actual school but that are not part of the school curriculum.

4. In relation to the item "Parents never get a mental break from their children, even when they are physically apart," the translation of the item should maintain the negative connotations included in this statement. It is meant to pick this up, and not that parents are so fulfilled by parenting that it overflows into all their thinking.

5. In relation to the item "Finding the best educational opportunities for children is important even before they go to school", the question refers to educational places and activities before they enter the school system.

6. In relation to the item "It is important to interact regularly with children on their level (e.g., getting down on the floor and playing with them)", the question refers to interacting and playing with children in a way they can enjoy at their stage of development, both physically and mentally.

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